

Numerical Solution of Heat Transfer by Conduction:

Notes for Engineering Education

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Index

Preliminary note	2
1. The Control Volume Method	3
1.1 Explicit Method	6
1.2 Implicit Method	7
1.3 Boundary conditions	7
2. Solving The Algebraic Equations	8
2.1 Convergence	9
2.2 Relaxation	9
3. Application example	11
3.1 The steady-state solution	11
3.2 Simulation of the evolution over time	13
References	15
Appendix A – Numerical solution of the temporal evolution using python	16

Preliminary Note

The first version of these notes was written in the 1999/2000 academic year to support the teaching of the "Heat and Mass Transfer II" curricular unit of the Mechanical Engineering degree at Instituto Superior Técnico (IST) to complement the existing bibliographic material and facilitate the understanding of numerical methods applied to heat conduction.

This revised edition was developed within the scope of the "Integrating Project for the 1st Cycle in Mechanical Engineering" curricular unit of the current Degree in Mechanical Engineering (LEMec21) at IST. In this updated context, these notes provide the foundation for developing a Python script to numerically simulate a heat conduction problem relevant to an industrial stamping process.

To facilitate this, we include an applied example that demonstrates both steady-state solutions and transient thermal evolution simulations. The numerical model and its computational implementation in Python are detailed in appendix.

1. The Control Volume Method

These notes outline the essential steps for discretizing the general heat transfer equation using the finite difference method and the control volume technique. The first version, originally written in Portuguese, dates back to 2001 (e.g., [1]) and was based on the more detailed description found in [2].

The differential equation for two-dimensional heat transfer by conduction in Cartesian coordinates is represented by the expression:

$$\rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) + g \quad (1)$$

where ρ represents the specific mass, c_p is the specific heat, k is the thermal conductivity, T is the temperature, and g is the rate of heat generation per unit volume.

The integration, in time and space, of the general heat transfer equation provides a continuous temperature solution. By discretizing this equation, we obtain the temperature value only at some points in the domain and, if the problem is transient, at specific instants of time.

The discretization method presented below is based on dividing the solution domain into a set of cells, or control volumes, and determining a set of algebraic equations written for each cell.

In each control volume, a point, or node of the grid, is defined at which the temperature value is to be known. To facilitate the explanation, the following figure shows a typical control volume of a two-dimensional problem in Cartesian coordinates.

Figure 1 – Two-dimensional control volume

This figure also presents the notation used in the discretization process. The central point, corresponding to the control volume of interest, is denoted as P , and the points corresponding to the neighboring control volumes are denoted as N , S , E , and W . The points n , s , e , and w are placed on the surfaces of the control volume and on the lines joining two consecutive nodes. These indices are also used to identify the components of the control surface. The variables δx and δy define the dimensions of the control volume, and δx_{PW} , δx_{EP} , δy_{PS} , and δy_{NP} represent the distances between the node P and the nodes W , E , S , and N , respectively.

$$k_e \approx \frac{k_E + k_P}{2} \quad (4.5)$$

$$k_w \approx \frac{k_P + k_W}{2} \quad (4.6)$$

Proceeding identically for the term (c), we obtain:

$$(c) = a_N(T_N - T_P) + a_S(T_S - T_P) \quad (5.1)$$

being:

$$a_N = k_n \frac{\delta x}{\delta y_{NP}} \quad (5.2)$$

$$a_S = k_s \frac{\delta x}{\delta y_{PS}} \quad (5.3)$$

$$k_n \approx \frac{k_N + k_P}{2} \quad (5.4)$$

$$k_s \approx \frac{k_P + k_S}{2} \quad (5.5)$$

The analysis of the terms (a), (b), and (c) reveals that these represent the heat fluxes that enter the control volume through its faces due to the temperature differences between point P and its neighbors. Thus, we conclude that the coefficients a_n ($n \in \{N, S, E, W\}$) represent the inverse of the thermal conduction resistance between node P and its neighboring nodes.

The source term can be a function of temperature. Since the discretized equations are linear, the term (d) is evaluated considering a linear dependence of the source term on temperature:

$$(d) = g \delta V = S_P T_P + S_U \quad (6)$$

Assuming that the temporal average of terms (b), (c), and (d) can be obtained from a linear combination of their values at two consecutive instants, equation (2) is also modified using the following relation:

$$\frac{1}{\delta t} \int_t^{t+\delta t} \{F\} dt = f \{F\} + (1-f) \{F\}^0 \quad (7)$$

where f represents the weighting factor.

The values of $f = 0$ and $f = 1$ correspond to assuming that the function F is constant during the time interval and that it varies discretely from one instant to the next. The assumptions made regarding this parameter generally lead to the identification of three different methods: Explicit ($f = 0$), Implicit ($f = 1$), and Crank-Nicolson ($f = 0.5$).

The temporal evolution of F assumed in each of these methods is illustrated in the following figure:

Figure 2 – Temporal evolution of F according to the method.
a) implicit, b) explicit, c) Crank-Nicolson

Figure 2 illustrates that, in the explicit method, the variation of the function is considered to occur at the end of the time interval. In contrast, in the implicit method, it occurs at the beginning. In the Crank-Nicolson method, a linear variation of F is considered. Computational constraints generally condition the choice of one of these methods.

Introducing into equation (2) the results corresponding to the terms (a), (b), (c), and (d), the following expression is obtained:

$$D_p(T_p - T_p^0) = f \left\{ \sum_n a_n (T_n - T_p) + S_p T_p + S_U \right\} + (1 - f) \left\{ \sum_n a_n (T_n - T_p) + S_p T_p + S_U \right\}^0 \quad (8)$$

1.1 Explicit method

Considering $f = 0$, the previous equation takes the following form:

$$D_p T_p = \left(D_p - \sum_n a_n + S_p \right) T_p^0 + \sum_n a_n T_n^0 + S_U \quad (9)$$

This equation illustrates that, in this case, the temperature value at point P at a given instant is only a function of the temperature at the previous instant at that point and neighboring points.

This apparent advantage, however, is counteracted by the possibility of obtaining physically unrealistic solutions. To avoid this problem, the coefficient of T_p^0 should be positive, as are the other coefficients. The need for this condition can be justified by noting that an increase in temperature at a point must lead to an increase in the temperature of neighboring points. As a consequence of introducing this condition, the discretizations of space and time are not independent.

For example, in a two-dimensional situation, with no source terms and with $\delta x = \delta y$, the condition $D_p - \sum a_n + S_p > 0$ leads to the result:

$$\delta t < \frac{\rho c_p}{4k} \delta x^2 \quad (10)$$

From this condition it follows that in this case, as δx is reduced, to increase precision, δt has to decrease much more.

1.2 Implicit method

To unconditionally guarantee that negative coefficients do not occur, it is necessary to consider $f = 1$. In this case, the discretized equation takes the form:

$$\left(D_p + \sum_n a_n - S_p \right) T_p = \sum_n a_n T_n + S_U + D_p T_p^0 \quad (11)$$

where it must be ensured that $S_p < 0$. This equation can also be written in other forms, through the following groupings of coefficients:

$$S'_U = S_U + D_p T_p^0 \quad (12.1)$$

$$S'_p = S_p - D_p \quad (12.2)$$

which lead to the following expression:

$$\left(\sum_n a_n - S'_p \right) T_p = \sum_n a_n T_n + S'_U \quad (12.3)$$

1.3 Boundary conditions

Boundary conditions can be incorporated, in general, by evaluating the heat flux entering the control volume through the boundary and introducing it as a source, using the terms S_U and S_p . As an example, the case of an element whose west face is subject to convection is illustrated below:

Figure 3 – Control volume with west face subject to convection

The amount of heat entering through the west face, per unit of time, is given by:

$$Q_w = \frac{T_\infty - T_P}{R_T} = -\frac{1}{R_T} T_P + \frac{T_\infty}{R_T} \quad (13.1)$$

being:

$$R_T = \frac{\delta x^*}{\delta y k} + \frac{1}{\delta y h} \quad (13.2)$$

In this situation, the algebraic equation for point P is transformed into the following:

$$\left(\sum_{n \neq W} a_n - S'_P \right) T_P = \sum_{n \neq W} a_n T_n + S'_U + \frac{T_\infty - T_P}{R_T} \quad (14.1)$$

which can be written in the form:

$$\left[\sum_{n \neq W} a_n - \left(S'_P - \frac{1}{R_T} \right) \right] T_P = \sum_{n \neq W} a_n T_n + \left(S'_U + \frac{T_\infty}{R_T} \right) \quad (14.2)$$

Recalculating, again, the value of the source terms and considering $a_w = 0$, we obtain:

$$\left(\sum_n a_n - S''_P \right) T_P = \sum_n a_n T_n + S''_U \quad (15.1)$$

being:

$$S''_P = S'_P - \frac{1}{R_T} \quad (15.2)$$

$$S''_U = S'_U + \frac{T_\infty}{R_T} \quad (15.3)$$

These expressions allow us to conclude that the structure of the initial equation is not changed due to the introduction of boundary conditions.

2. Solving The Algebraic Equations

The consideration of non-linear source terms is possible if iterative methods are used. Additionally, when the number of nodes considered is large, the use of these methods to solve the system of algebraic equations is also advantageous and, in general, necessary.

The Gauss-Seidel method is the simplest of the iterative methods (e.g. [3]). This method consists of traversing all the nodes and determining the temperature at each node using the most recent temperature values involved, according to the following expression:

$$T_p = \sum_n \frac{a_n}{a_p} T_n^* + \frac{S_U''}{a_p} \quad (16)$$

where $a_p = \sum a_n - S_p''$ and T_n^* represents the most recent temperature value at node n .

In one-dimensional situations, the matrix of the system of equations is tridiagonal. In this case, if the source terms are linear, the system of equations can be solved by the Gaussian elimination method (e.g. [4]). In this case, the solution can be obtained using the Thomas algorithm, which takes advantage of the tridiagonal structure of the matrix of the system of equations (e.g. [5]).

In two and three-dimensional situations, a method known as the line-by-line method is often employed, which combines the direct method for one-dimensional situations with the Gauss-Seidel method. In this method, a line is chosen (for example, a line with a constant x value), and the values of T on the neighboring lines are assumed to be known and equal to their most recent values. The values of T along the considered line are calculated using the Gaussian elimination method (e.g. [2]).

2.1 Convergence

An iterative process converges when the value of the dependent variables evolves smoothly from an initial set of estimated values to an acceptable solution of the discretized equations.

In this type of problem, a residual source is generally defined from the following expression (e.g. [2]):

$$R = \sum_p \left[a_p T_p - \left(\sum_n a_n T_n + S_U'' \right) \right] \quad (17.1)$$

Moreover, the reduction of the source to a sufficiently small prescribed value is used as the convergence criterion:

$$\frac{R}{Q_{ref}} < \varepsilon \quad (17.2)$$

where Q_{ref} represents a reference value related to the total heat transferred per unit of time, and ε represents an infinitesimal dimensionless value related to the desired accuracy.

2.2 Relaxation

In the iterative process used to solve algebraic equations, it is often desirable to smooth out variations in temperature values from one iteration to the next.

The relaxation process consists of replacing the value calculated in one iteration with a linear combination of the values from the last two iterations (e.g. [2]):

$$T_p = \beta T_p^n + (1 - \beta) T_p^{n-1} \quad (18)$$

where β is called the relaxation factor ($0 < \beta \leq 1$), T_p^{n-1} represents the value of T_p^n in the previous iteration, and T_p^n represents the value that would be obtained if relaxation were not considered. The value of T_p^n can be defined from the expression:

$$T_p^n = \frac{\sum a_n T_n + S_U''}{a_p} \quad (19)$$

Substituting this expression into the previous equation, we obtain:

$$\frac{a_p}{\beta} T_p = \sum_n a_n T_n + \left[S_U'' + (1 - \beta) \frac{a_p}{\beta} T_p^{n-1} \right] \quad (20)$$

and, recalculating the values of a_p and S_U , we obtain:

$$a_p' T_p = \sum_n a_n T_n + S_U''' \quad (21.1)$$

being:

$$a_p' = \frac{a_p}{\beta} \quad (21.2)$$

$$S_U''' = S_U'' + (1 - \beta) a_p' T_p^{n-1} \quad (21.3)$$

These expressions allow us to conclude that considering relaxation also does not change the original structure of the system of equations.

3. Application Example

A carbon steel bar with an L-shaped cross-section is placed on a surface maintained at 150 °C. The thermal contact resistance at the interface is modeled using a contact conductance of 1000 W/m²K. The material properties of the bar are as follows: thermal conductivity $k = 50$ W/mK, $\rho = 8000$ kg/m³, and specific heat capacity $c_p = 500$ J/kgK. The bar is exposed to convective cooling from ambient air at 20 °C, with a convective heat transfer coefficient $h = 10$ W/m²K.

Figure 4 – Discretization of the L-shaped cross-section of the carbon steel bar

The objective is twofold:

1. To evaluate the steady-state temperature distribution at the nodes shown in the figure.
2. To analyze and present the transient temperature evolution at these nodes over time.

3.1 The steady-state solution

To evaluate the steady-state temperatures of the nodes, we must construct the system of algebraic heat balance equations for the control volumes related to the nodes represented in Figure 4.

To write these equations, we can start from equations (15.1), (15.2) and (15.3), presented in the previous section, which already include the modifications related to the boundary conditions.

Although the geometry of the bar section is two-dimensional, we have the horizontal (x) and vertical (y) directions, but we can model the heat transfer problem as being one-dimensional. In fact, we can say that each control volume exchanges heat with its neighbors, to the left and to the right, and with the environment.

Under these conditions, for example for volume 2, we can write the following heat balance equation:

$$(a_{L(2)} + a_{R(2)} - S_{P(2)})T_{(2)} = a_{L(2)}T_{(1)} + a_{R(2)}T_{(3)} + S_{U(2)}$$

Due to the symmetry of the geometry of the control volumes ($\Delta x = \Delta y = 0.02$ m) the coefficients of the balance equation related to the neighboring nodes are all the same. Thus, for example, the coefficient $a_{L(2)}$ can be evaluated as shown below:

$$a_{L(2)} = k \frac{A_{12}}{L_{12}} = k \times \frac{\Delta y \times 1}{\Delta x} = 50 \text{ W/K}$$

Therefore, since we are considering steady state, before considering the effects of boundary conditions, we can write for control volume 2:

$$(100 - S_{P2})T_2 = 50 T_1 + 50 T_3 + S_{U2}$$

Let us now consider the influence of boundary conditions. In control volume 2, we have contact with a hot surface on the southern boundary and contact with ambient air on the northern boundary.

The heat received (per unit time) by volume 2, through the southern boundary, can be evaluated from the following expression:

$$Q_s = \frac{T_s - T_2}{R_{Ts}} = -\frac{T_2}{R_{Ts}} + \frac{T_s}{R_{Ts}}$$

The thermal resistance R_{Ts} has two components, one due to the contact resistance between the two surfaces and the other due to the conduction resistance between the southern surface and the center of the control volume:

$$R_{Ts} = \frac{1}{A \times h_c} + \frac{L}{A \times k} = \frac{1}{\Delta x \times 1 \times h_c} + \frac{\Delta y / 2}{\Delta x \times 1 \times k} = \frac{1}{0.02 \times 1000} + \frac{0.01}{0.02 \times 50} = 0.06 \text{ K/W}$$

Therefore, the contribution of heat exchanged across the southern boundary to the source terms is as follows:

$$S_{P2s} = -\frac{1}{0.06} = -16.667 \text{ W/K}$$

$$S_{U2s} = \frac{150}{0.06} = 2500 \text{ W}$$

The accounting for heat exchanged across the northern boundary is similar. In this case we have to replace, in the previous expressions, h_c by h_a , and T_s by T_a :

$$R_{Tn} = \frac{1}{A \times h_a} + \frac{L}{A \times k} = \frac{1}{\Delta x \times 1 \times h_a} + \frac{\Delta y / 2}{\Delta x \times 1 \times k} = \frac{1}{0.02 \times 10} + \frac{0.01}{0.02 \times 50} = 5.01 \text{ K/W}$$

Thus, the contribution of heat exchanged across the northern boundary to the source terms of control volume 2 is as follows:

$$S_{P2n} = -\frac{1}{5.01} = -0.1996 \text{ W/K}$$

$$S_{U2n} = \frac{20}{5.01} = 3.992 \text{ W}$$

Combining the results of the two boundaries we obtain the source terms for control volume 2, as shown below:

$$S_{p2} = S_{p2s} + S_{p2n} = -16.6667 - 0.1996 = -16.8663 \text{ W/K}$$

$$S_{U2} = S_{U2s} + S_{U2n} = 2500 + 3.992 = 2503.992 \text{ W}$$

Adding the source terms to the balance equation for control volume 2 we obtain:

$$116.866 T_2 = 50 T_1 + 50 T_3 + 2503.99$$

And, proceeding identically, we obtain for control volumes 1, 3, 4 and 5, respectively, the following equations:

$$67.066 T_1 = 50 T_2 + 2507.98$$

$$116.866 T_3 = 50 T_2 + 50 T_4 + 2503.99$$

$$100.399 T_4 = 50 T_3 + 50 T_5 + 7.98$$

$$50.599 T_5 = 50 T_4 + 11.98$$

Finally, solving the system of equations, we obtain the temperature values at each of the nodes, as shown below:

$$[146.14, 145.86, 144.70, 142.27, 140.83]$$

3.2 Simulation of the evolution over time

To simulate the temporal evolution of temperatures at the nodes, we must discretize time and modify the algebraic equations, introducing terms related to thermal inertia and the temperature field at the previous instant.

To consider the spatial and temporal discretizations as independent, we opted to use the implicit temporal discretization, as illustrated in subsection 1.2. Accordingly, we adopted a time step of 5 seconds and a simulation duration of 1500 seconds (25 minutes, 300 steps).

As we can see from equation (11) and equations (12.1) and (12.2), the source terms now include terms involving the thermal inertia coefficient D_p , which we can evaluate as shown below:

$$D_p = \frac{\rho c_p}{\delta t} \delta V = \frac{8000 \times 500}{5} \times 0.02 \times 0.02 = 320 \text{ W/K}$$

To illustrate the changes in the algebraic equations, we consider the equation for control volume 2:

$$(116.866 + 320) T_2 = 50 T_1 + 50 T_3 + (2503.99 + 320 \times T_2^0)$$

where T_2^0 represents the temperature at node 2 in the previous instant.

As we can see, the central coefficient (a_p) changes but does not vary over time. However, the independent source term (S_u) changes and varies over time because it depends on the temperature value at the previous instant.

Therefore, the computational implementation must take these aspects into account; essentially, we have to repeat the formulation and solution of a problem many times, as illustrated in the previous section for the steady-state case.

An example of the implementation of the transient solution in Python is presented in Appendix A. The simulation results obtained are shown graphically in the following figure.

Figure 5 – Simulation of temperature evolution at nodes

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Appendix A – Numerical solution of the temporal evolution using python

```

import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from pathlib import Path
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

# Problem parameters
TA = 20.0
HA = 10.0
TS = 150.0
HC = 1000
DEN = 8000.0
CP = 500.0
K = 50.00

# Number of nodes and dimensions
NI = 5
WX = 0.06
HY = 0.06

# Discretization parameters
DX = WX/(NI-2)
DY = HY/(NI-2)

# Time step (s) and total time (s)
DT = 5.0
TT = 0.0

# Number of time steps
NT = 300

# Vectors of the main variables
AL = np.zeros(NI)
AR = np.zeros(NI)
AP = np.zeros(NI)
SP = np.zeros(NI)
SB = np.zeros(NI)
SU = np.zeros(NI)
TP = np.full(NI,TA)
TP0 = np.full(NI,TA)

# Configuration of boundary conditions
# Due to the simplicity of the geometry,
# we adopted node 2 as a reference.
RC = 0.5*DY/(DX*K)
RHA = 1.0/(DX*HA)
RHC = 1.0/(DX*HC)
RTA = RC + RHA
RTC = RC + RHC

# Node 1: South, West and North boundary
SP[0] = -(1.0/RTC + 2.0/RTA)

```

```

SB[0] = TS/RTC + 2.0*TA/RTA

# Node 2: South and North boundary
SP[1] = -(1.0/RTC + 1.0/RTA)
SB[1] = TS/RTC + TA/RTA

# Node 3: South and East boundary
SP[2] = -(1.0/RTC + 1.0/RTA)
SB[2] = TS/RTC + TA/RTA

# Node 4: West and East boundary
SP[3] = -2.0/RTA
SB[3] = 2.0*TA/RTA

# Node 5: West, East and North boundary
SP[4] = -3.0/RTA
SB[4] = 3.0*TA/RTA

# Configuration of connections between nodes
AIJ = K*DY/DX
# > Neighbors on the right:
for i in range(NI-1):
    AR[i] = AIJ
# > Neighbors on the left:
for i in range(1, NI):
    AL[i] = AR[i-1]

# Central coefficients of nodes
DP = DEN*CP*DX*DY/DT
for i in range(NI):
    AP[i] = DP + AR[i] + AL[i] - SP[i]

# Structure for storing results
results = {'Time': []}
for i in range(1, NI+1):
    results[f'TP{i}'] = []

# Saving the initial conditions
results['Time'].append(TT)
for i in range(NI):
    results[f'TP{i+1}'].append(TP[i])

# Time Cycle
A = np.zeros(NI)
C = np.zeros(NI)
for IT in range(1, NT+1):
    TT += DT
    # Updating transient source terms
    for i in range(NI):
        SU[i] = SB[i] + DP*TP0[i]
    # Solution of the system of equations: Thomas algorithm
    # > Condensation

```

```

A[0] = AR[0]/AP[0]
C[0] = SU[0]/AP[0]
for i in range(1, NI):
    A[i] = AR[i]
    C[i] = SU[i]
    Bval = AL[i]
    Dval = AP[i]
    TERM = 1.0/(Dval - Bval*A[i-1])
    A[i] = A[i]*TERM
    C[i] = (C[i] + Bval*C[i-1])*TERM
# > Inverse substitution
TP[NI-1] = C[NI-1]
for i in range(NI-2, -1, -1):
    TP[i] = A[i]*TP[i+1] + C[i]
# Updating previous temperature
TP0 = TP
# Store results
results['Time'].append(TT)
for i in range(NI):
    results[f'TP{i+1}'].append(TP[i])

# Processing and saving results
# > Convert results to DataFrame
results_df = pd.DataFrame(results)
# > Create results folder, if it does not exist
output_dir = Path('results')
output_dir.mkdir(exist_ok=True)
# > Save results_df in a file
filename = 'heat_conduction_results.csv'
csv_path = output_dir / filename
results_df.to_csv(csv_path, index=False)
print(f"\nResults saved to {csv_path}")

# Evolution of temperatures over time
tp_cols = list(results_df.columns[1:])
results_df.plot(x='Time', y=tp_cols)
plt.ylabel('Temperature (°C)')
plt.xlabel('Time (s)')
plt.title('Temperature Evolution at Nodes')
# Saving the graph
filename = 'temperature_evolution.png'
plot_path = output_dir / filename
plt.savefig(plot_path, dpi=300, bbox_inches='tight', format='png')
plt.show()
print(f"\nGraph saved in: {plot_path}")

```